

Milestone: M6.4 Project impact and monitoring indicators presented to OG

Lead Participant:

ELIXIR/EMBL/EBI

Author:

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Due:

30 Sep 2021

Date Of Completion:

27/12/2022

Means of Verification

B1MG updates provided during the regular 1+MG Group meetings until 30/09/2021

- [Link to folder with presentations](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes, Due to

- the need to report progress to the 1+MG group;
- the duplicity of members between the B1MG Governing board and the 1+MG Group and;
- the need to update to the evolving needs to the initiative.

This milestone has been replaced by the periodic project updates (quarterly) to the 1+MG Group plenary available [here](#)

Project participants & others

Coordinator: Serena Scollen, Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub)
WP1: Ruben Kok (DTL-Projects)
WP2: Regina Becker (UNILU)
WP3: Ivo Gut (CRG), Jeroen Belien (VUmc)
WP4: Dylan Spalding, Tommi Nyrönen (CSC)
WP5: Astrid Vicente (INSA), Serena Scollen (ELIXIR Hub), Ilse Custers (Lygature)
WP6: Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub), Esther Rodriguez (ISCIII)

Next action steps

N/A

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